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ОСОБЕННОСТИ ПРОВЕДЕНИЯ ИНТЕГРИРОВАННОГО УРОКА С ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕМ МЕТОДИКИ CLIL

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FEATURES OF THE INTEGRATED LESSON USING THE CLIL METHODOLOGY

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Аннотация

В статье рассматривается технология интегрированного образования и предметно-языковая интегрированная методика (CLIL), который в настоящее время характеризуется в мировой научно-методической литературе как один из инновационных подходов к организации билингвального обучения и предполагает реализацию одновременно двух целей обучения в двух предметных областях – языковой и предметной. Перечисляются дидактические требования для межпредметного интегрированного урока. Представляются различные трактовки его сущности, выделяются его особенности реализации в билингвальном обучении посредством применения его основных принципов и стратегий.

Abstract

The article considers the technology of integrated education and the content-language integrated methodology (CLIL), which is currently characterized in the world scientific and methodological literature as one of the innovative approaches to the organization of bilingual education and involves the implementation of two learning goals simultaneously in two subject areas – language and content. The didactic requirements for an interdisciplinary integrated lesson are listed. Various interpretations of its essence are presented, its features of implementation in bilingual education through the application of its basic principles and strategies are highlighted.

Ключевые слова: Технология интегрированного образования, бинарный урок, межпредметная связь, CLIL (Content Language Integrated Learning), предметно-ориентированный подход.

Keywords: Technology of integrated education, binary lesson, interdisciplinary communication, CLIL (Content Language Integrated Learning), subject-oriented approach.

Currently, the integration of education implies the introduction of the principles of integration into all components of the educational process, which ensures not only its integrity, but also consistency. Integration processes imply a qualitative transformation of the education system.

The technology of integrated education is such an organization of the learning process, which implies the inclusion of binary learning lessons, as well as lessons using interdisciplinary connections. The CLIL methodology is widely used for the effective implementation of integrated education. Accordingly, the purpose of this article is to identify the effectiveness of the CLIL methodology in conducting an integrated lesson for school-age students.

I.D. Zverev was one of the first to define integration as a pedagogical phenomenon. The scientist noted that integration in teaching is carried out by combining elements of different academic subjects in one synthesized course, confluence of scientific concepts and methods of different disciplines into general scientific concepts and methods of cognition, integration and summing up the foundations of sciences in the disclosure of interdisciplinary educational problems. [1]

The following competencies are formed in the integrated lessons:

- 1) value-semantic (understanding the purpose of the lesson, the importance of the topic being studied);
- 2) general cultural;
- 3) informational (working with a computer, the ability to independently select the necessary material);
- 4) communicative (ability to work in groups, listen, communicate, be loyal to people with a different point of view).

The integration of subjects in modern education is one of the directions of active search for new pedagogical solutions that contribute to the improvement of the teaching staff, the development of creative potentials of teaching teams and individual teachers in order to have a more effective impact on students.

Didactic requirements for an integrated lesson:

1. A lesson with interdisciplinary integration should have a clearly formulated educational and cognitive task, for the solution of which it is necessary to attract knowledge from other subjects.

2. At such a lesson, high activity and interest of students in the application of knowledge from other subjects should be ensured. To do this, repeated conversations are conducted, revealing knowledge from other subjects; problematic situations are created, problematic issues are raised that require knowledge from related subjects; preliminary homework is given; a

combination of individual and group tasks (by interests, by choice, mandatory) with collective learning work in the classroom is provided; extracurricular work is used, etc.

3. Interdisciplinary connections in the lesson should not be external or artificial in nature. They should contribute to students' understanding of the essence of the concepts and phenomena being studied. The deepening of general interdisciplinary concepts (laws) occurs when teachers of related subjects coordinate their interpretation among themselves, apply special methodological techniques for fixing and systematizing concepts. To systematize interdisciplinary concepts, it is advisable to compile generalizing tables on individual academic topics or academic problems of interdisciplinary content.

4. An interdisciplinary integrated lesson should contain conclusions of a philosophical, generalized nature, based on the connection of knowledge from different subjects. So students can realize the unity of nature, the laws by which it exists.

5. An integrated lesson should evoke a positive attitude of students, arouse their interest in learning the connections between knowledge from different courses. This is achieved in the following ways:

- establishing links between interdisciplinary cognitive tasks with the life and practical activities of students;
- solving computational problems of interdisciplinary content;
- performing practical, laboratory, independent work on an interdisciplinary basis;
- the use of visual aids from other subjects (tables, diagrams, graphs, drawings, etc.), scientific and popular additional literature having a borderline interscientific character.

6. An interdisciplinary lesson should always be aimed at generalizing certain sections of the educational material of related courses for the formation of a natural-scientific understanding of the world of students.

The experience of generalizing integrative lessons of many researchers has shown that in order to conduct it, it is initially necessary to integrate the content, i.e. educational material. Then integrate it into the learning technology. In practice, the path to integration in the classroom begins with the use of interdisciplinary tasks, the interdisciplinary composition of new educational material, integrative forms of control. And only then they conduct a lesson.

Currently, there are several already developed methods and technologies for the effective implementation of an integrated lesson in the curriculum, especially for integrated lessons, where English is the second subject. Now, this language is in great demand, and is being very intensively introduced into the educational program. One of the most well-known and effective methods is considered to be CLIL.

The CLIL (Content and Language Integrated Learning) methodology is one of the versions of bilingual education, where contents are taught in foreign languages. But it is important to focus on the fact that it considers learning a foreign language more

as a tool for studying other subjects, and not vice versa. That is, we do not study English, we study a special subject using English.

The founder of this approach is D. Marsh. According to his interpretation, content-language integrated learning is based on two main goals: the study of the content of this discipline and the simultaneous study of a foreign language. Modern educational literature gives this methodology the following definition: CLIL is a didactic technique that allows students to form linguistic and communicative competencies in a non-native language in the same educational context in which they have the formation and development of general academic knowledge and skills.

One of the features of CLIL is that it can adapt to traditional school curricula - the study of one particular content through a foreign language, and also exist independently of them: to study several disciplines in interrelation at once. It is only necessary to take into account that CLIL implies the simultaneous study of a subject and a foreign language, and it is impossible to ignore their relationship when using CLIL. [2] In other words, there are two approaches to implementing CLIL [3]:

- 1) subject-oriented, in which learning is focused on the content of the discipline;
- 2) linguistically-oriented is aimed at learning a foreign language through the subject.

But mostly many teachers focus on the first, subject-oriented approach. They use a foreign language only as a means of teaching a subject. Therefore, when preparing a teacher for a lesson based on the material of knowledge of related disciplines, it begins with studying programs on subjects and determining the interrelationships of educational topics. This allows the teacher to study the educational material of related subjects, prepare textbooks and visual aids from other courses, offer students homework to repeat the basic knowledge on interrelated subjects, get the necessary advice from subject teachers.

Also, at the beginning of the implementation of the content-language integrated approach (CLIL), the teacher must take into account the correct definition of the object of study; the correct selection of material taking into account the psychological aspects of cognitive activity; as well as the mandatory consideration of age characteristics. That is, the teacher needs to analyze and select the necessary educational and methodological material corresponding to the level of knowledge of a foreign language, in particular English, and the profile subject of students. It is worth noting that the level of cognitive abilities of students should be determined as accurately as possible, since too simple or, conversely, complex material is likely to negatively affect the level of motivation of students.

Summing up, it is possible to determine a number of tasks that the teacher faces when preparing lessons in the format of the described methodology:

- 1) the material on the academic subject in terms of complexity should be slightly inferior to the level of knowledge of students on this subject in their native language;

2) tasks should reflect the peculiarities of the language being studied, work out the ability to use certain linguistic forms;

3) the texts should be selected in accordance with the topic and the actual level of knowledge of the students;

4) tasks should correspond to the subject and contain sufficient amount of information for understanding and assimilation.

To sum up, we can say that the application of the content-language integration methodology has a number of positive and effective sides in teaching. Among which it allows to teach students to consciously and freely use a foreign language in everyday communication; to expand the horizons of students; to prepare students for continuing education in their chosen specialty; to develop and improve communicative competencies through learning a foreign language.

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